

A Virtual View of NOIRLab's Programs and Facilities

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In late October 2022, we announced the release of the virtual tours for all seven NOIRLab base and summit facilities. In these tours you will find an impressive array of photospheres (images of environments digitally projected on a sphere) arranged into cohesive virtual tours of our summit facilities, staff and equipment, day and nighttime vistas, and more. Here we offer a “peak behind the curtain,” if you will, of the tours and their creation.

Inception

One of the areas that the NOIRLab Communications, Education & Engagement (CEE) group has expanded into is immersive virtual experiences. Staff therefore set out on an

ambitious plan to not only document our sites with ultra-high-definition video and photographs (as we never have before) with high-quality full-dome visuals to be used in planetariums, but also put into a unified virtual experience that anyone with internet access can visit from anywhere in the world.

The International Gemini Observatory and Vera C. Rubin Observatory have both previously created virtual products, creating a virtual tour of Gemini and 360° videos during the construction of Rubin. However, with the changes to our facilities and the improvements in technologies used in virtual tours, we decided it was time for an update.

Figures 1&2: Behind the scenes photos from the 'photo expedition.'
Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/J. Pollard

Background Image: Panoramic view of the Gemini North telescope, part of the International Gemini Observatory, a Program of NSF's NOIRLab. Credit: NOIRLab/AURA/NSF/P. Horálek

Photography

In 2022, NOIRLab arranged for three experienced photographers and videographers—Petr Horálek, Theofanis Matsopoulos, and Tomáš Slovinský (figures 1&2)—to work with NOIRLab’s own photographers on a ‘photo expedition’. Over the course of 21 days, the highly skilled photographers worked with local guides at each facility to fully document

and capture the location, which resulted in an amazing 320 photospheres.

To achieve high-quality images, with up to 500-megapixels resolution, modified¹ DSLR cameras and special panorama equipment were used. Nighttime 360-degree photospheres are even more challenging. Much like the telescopes we are photographing, it is important to optimize the signal-to-noise ratio, such that a setting is used that is sufficiently sensitive and balanced with the exposure time—this is where the modified DSLR cameras come into play. On top of this, if the exposure time is not calculated perfectly for each shot, the sky will have shifted by the time you swing around and take the last images of the photospheres.

¹ The default integrated infrared-cutoff filter on the CMOS sensor of the cameras was replaced with a broader bandwidth filter to increase the camera sensitivity between 550 and 710 nm, particularly to significantly increase the sensitivity to the ionized hydrogen (H α) emission line at 656 nm.

Post-Processing

After all of the images were collected, 6 to 24 photos were selected for each scene, and then stitched into a single photosphere (also referred to as “panoramas” in this article) in equirectangular plate carrée projection (mapping a sphere to a flat page such as the globe to an equirectangular map figure 3). After that, we ensured that natural colors in each panorama were preserved and white-balanced.

Color balancing is an important process to visually enhance the immersive experience for all of the day and nighttime images. It also ensures that colors in the nighttime images are the closest representation of what the human eye would see if capable of detecting the details and faint colors of the night sky. The limited low-light vision of human eyes does not allow for the perception of most colors in very dark conditions, like those in and around NOIRLab’s observing facilities at night.

The next step focused on manually removing stitching errors/artifacts and

then color correcting each individual panorama. As the final step of post-processing, most of the panoramas were re-projected into a hemispherical image with fish-eye projection to be compatible in planetariums (figure 4).

Production

The primary objective of the virtual tour project is to produce seven different virtual tours, (one for each NOIRLab facility), including base and summit facilities. To maximize device compatibility, this meant building interfaces from scratch for each virtual tour: two for widescreen devices (one each for desktops and tablets), one for smartphones, and one for Virtual Reality (VR) headsets (figure 5). The interfaces were designed with considerations including how the images look on each device, how the user will interact with it, and what kind of information will be overlaid on top of the image content.

Our production team mapped out the locations, geotagged each panorama, directed camera movement for each area of interest in every panorama, and solicited input from the content experts at each site so that we would be sure to include the areas that were most significant or interesting. We conducted an iterative process with prototypes going through alpha testing by NOIRLab colleagues and updating and then beta testing of the selected version.

To increase the user interactivity and aesthetics, we implemented visual effects such as lens flare, rain, a panorama-to-panorama walkthrough effect, Virtual Reality video implementation, and informative popup text bubbles and labels. The

Figure 4: Full-dome image of Gemini South and the SOAR telescope on Cerro Pachón in Chile, illuminated by the Milky Way’s glow. Gemini South can be seen projecting a laser guide star (LGS) into the night sky. These images are also ideal for use in planetariums.
Credit: International Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/P. Horálek

Figure 3: 360 panoramic view of the Chilean night sky as the Milky Way streaks above Vera C. Rubin Observatory and the Rubin Auxiliary Telescope (left) on Cerro Pachón. Credit: Rubin Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/P. Horálek

popups were designed to be ‘discovered’ by users who want to spend more time exploring “books” in our facilities’ libraries, the night sky above the NOIRLab telescopes, or other telescopes visible in the daytime panoramas.

Accessibility and Future Updates

A critical goal of this project is to address accessibility issues inherent in visiting our remote facilities. We envision that these tours will be used by school groups who don’t have the resources or time to travel; by members of the public who, due to health or mobility concerns, are unable to go to our often inaccessible mountain summits; and by anyone who wants to come as close to experiencing the real thing as they can without actually traveling across the globe. It is our hope to continually improve accessibility and inclusion by creating highly immersive and interactive virtual experiences accessible from the comfort of home and compatible with a wide range of devices. A downloadable version for Windows and Mac desktops, which can be used without a high-speed internet connection, is available on each virtual tour web page.

With diversity and accessibility in mind, the NOIRLab Virtual Tour is a first step toward a globally accessible environment with features planned for future updates that will include toggling between preferred languages, text-to-speech for mobile users or people with limited vision using VR headsets, and live guided virtual tours for schools and group meetings.

In the coming months you can expect to see the addition of Spanish-language integration (we encourage other international partners throughout NOIRLab to consider working with us to make versions for additional languages as well). We will also be considering additional locations and different perspectives to further flesh out and expand the user experience. This will include updated and additional photography, video, and new interactive elements. The virtual tour is a dynamic experience, changing and updating to keep pace with the real world changes of our sites (Vera C. Rubin Observatory moving full into operation, changes as a result of the Contreras Fire on Kitt Peak, etc.).

If you haven’t had the opportunity to experience our virtual tours yet, please visit them and explore!